

<u>Nuffield Foundation</u>	
Data management plan required?	Yes
RDM policy Link	http://www.nuffieldfoundation.org/sites/default/files/files/Guide%20for%20Grant-Holders%20Jan%202018(1).pdf
Definition of data	Not specified
Length of data management plan	Not specified
DMP template/ requirements	If data is to be deposited in an archiving facility, which archive and how this data will be anonymised and the timescale of deposition and retention.
Required data repository	Not specified
Time for data release	Within 1 year of end of grant.
Time for long-term storage of data	Not specified
Costings	Any costs should be included in budget.
Last updated	Not known
Contact Details	info@nuffieldfoundation.org
Comments	N/A

Documents used:

Grants for research: Guide for grant holders.

[http://www.nuffieldfoundation.org/sites/default/files/files/Guide%20for%20Grant-Holders%20Jan%202018\(1\).pdf](http://www.nuffieldfoundation.org/sites/default/files/files/Guide%20for%20Grant-Holders%20Jan%202018(1).pdf)

Accessed: June 2018